

BEHOLDING THE GLORY OF THE LORD:
A TRANSFORMATIVE JOURNEY FROM GLORY TO GLORY

An Exegetical Essay on 2 Corinthians 3:18

Sean Shetler
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Dr. Chris Kugler

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I. Thesis

A. Thesis: From Glory to Glory – 2 Corinthians 3:18

In 2 Corinthians 3:18, Paul emphasizes that as believers behold the Lord's glory with unveiled faces, they are gradually transformed into Christ's image through the Holy Spirit, moving "from one degree of glory to another." This ongoing spiritual transformation contrasts the fading glory of the old covenant and anticipates the future, ultimate glorification. Conversely, Romans 8:18 affirms that current sufferings are insignificant compared to the future glory yet to be revealed, which culminates in Revelation 21:4, where God's renewal of creation brings a world free from death, mourning, and pain. Paul's use of "glory" serves not only to describe the believer's present sanctification but also points toward the ultimate, future glorification that believers will fully experience when they see Christ *face to face*.¹

¹ The term *vis-à-vis* originates from Latin via French, where it literally means "face-to-face," derived from the word *visage* (Latin: *facie ad faciem*). See Merriam-Webster, "Vis-à-Vis," *Merriam-Webster.com Dictionary*, <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/vis-à-vis>; In Greek, the term "πρόσωπον" (*prosōpon*) (Strong's # 4383) is commonly translated as "face," "countenance," or "visage" and appears 76 times in the New Testament (NT), with notable references in 1 Corinthians 13:12 and Matthew 18:10. See William D. Mounce, *Mounce's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1260.

II. Introduction

A. Introduction - Reflections on Eternity in *Christianity is Jewish* by Edith Schaeffer

In Chapter 18 (“Eighteen”) of *Christianity is Jewish*, Edith Schaeffer poignantly reflects on the believer’s journey toward eternity. She captures the Christian hope of experiencing God’s presence more fully, emphasizing that our current understanding is only a glimpse of the eternal glory to come. Schaeffer uses the analogy of a bird flying and occasionally touching down to describe our spiritual journey. Just as the bird lands briefly at different peaks (“or precipices”), we experience “touchpoints” (“or changes”) in life—moments of transformation through the Holy Spirit—that shape us. These milestones (“or gradual changes”) reflect the process of sanctification, ultimately preparing us for the fullness of joy and victory promised when all creation is renewed. This anticipation of meeting Christ face to face highlights the transformative power of faith and the hope of resurrection that sustains believers in their earthly walk. On page 205, she writes about glory, eternity, and meeting the Lord face to face: “As our bird’s flight through the Bible takes us to various places....we can only touch down at a few spots....God has given us glimpses of what is to come before we are with Him and see things ‘face to face.’ We are given a foretaste of the wonder and glory that awaits believers when the final victory is achieved, and we enter into eternity in our resurrected bodies.”²

² The author Edith Schaeffer and her husband, Dr. Francis Schaeffer, founded L’Abri Fellowship in the Swiss Alps, where thousands of questioning young men and women from many cultures and many professions have found spiritual help. Edith Schaeffer, *Christianity is Jewish* (Wheaton, IL: Tyndale House Publishers, 1975), 205.

B. Introduction - Future Glorification in *Vision at Patmos* by Catherine and Justo González

In 2 Corinthians 3:18, Paul describes the transformative journey of believers who, by beholding the glory of the Lord with unveiled faces, are being changed into Christ's image from one degree of glory to another. This ongoing sanctification, driven by the Holy Spirit, leads to a final fulfillment in which believers fully reflect God's glory. This transformative process reaches its fulfillment in Revelation 21:4, where God promises to wipe away every tear and eliminate death, mourning, crying, and pain.

The transformation Paul describes is completed in the new creation (Rev. 21:4), where the brokenness of this present world is replaced with the fullness of God's glory. As believers are perfected in the image of Christ, they enter a reality where all things are made new, reflecting the ultimate purpose of being conformed to the likeness of Christ in a world free from suffering and filled with God's eternal presence. Their hope was for a new ordering of city life, where God would "wipe away every tear from their eyes," and death could cease (Rev. 21:4).³

C. Introduction - Bible Verses

2 Corinthians 3:18 NRSV: "And all of us, with unveiled faces, seeing the glory of the Lord as though reflected in a mirror, are being transformed into the same image from one degree of glory

³ Revelation 21:4 describes how God will fully renew creation, erasing all sorrow and perfecting believers into His likeness, culminating in a world free from death, mourning, and pain. Catherine Gunsalus González and Justo Luis González, *Visions at Patmos: A Study of the Book of Revelation* (New York: Women's Division, Board of Global Ministries, The United Methodist Church, 1978), 113; See Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2228.

to another; for this comes from the Lord, the Spirit.”⁴

2 Corinthians 3:18 NET: “And we all, with unveiled faces reflecting the glory of the Lord, are being transformed into the same image from one degree of glory to another, which is from the Lord, who is the Spirit.”⁵

Romans 8:18 NRSV: “I consider that the sufferings of this present time are not worth comparing with the glory about to be revealed to us.”⁶

Romans 8:18 NET: “For I consider that our present sufferings cannot even be compared to the glory that will be revealed to us.”⁷

Revelation 21:4 NRSV: “He will wipe every tear from their eyes. Death will be no more;

⁴ In 2 Corinthians 3:18: The phrase “All of us” continues Paul’s emphasis on universality throughout the Corinthian letters. The reference to “unveiled faces” echoes Moses’ repeated unveiling in Exodus 34:34. The mention of glory “reflected in a mirror” may suggest the reflection of God’s glory in Christ (2 Cor. 4:6). Some translations render the verb differently, such as “to behold” or “to contemplate.” The idea of transformation into the divine image has roots in Hellenistic religion, as well as in Romans 8:29, 1 Corinthians 15:49, and Colossians 3:10. See Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2065.

⁵ In 2 Corinthians 3:18: (28) The Greek (Grk) is translated as “we all, with unveiled faces, beholding the glory of the Lord as in a mirror.” (29) The (Grk) phrase is translated as “from glory to glory.” (30) The (Grk) phrase is translated as “just as from.” (31) The (Grk) phrase “from the Lord, the Spirit” is translated with the genitive (pneumatōs) as a genitive of apposition. Daniel B. Wallace, Senior New Testament Editor, *The NET Bible: New English Translation*, 2nd ed. (Richardson, TX: Biblical Studies Press, 1997), 2116.

⁶ In Romans 8:18, the term “sufferings” refers to the hardships that believers face. See Romans 5:3-4 for further context. Being in Christ does not exempt believers from difficulties. “This present time” likely refers to what Paul describes as “the present evil age” in Galatians 1:4. For additional reference, see Romans 3:26. The term “glory” is discussed in Romans 5:2 and 5:18, and also in Philippians 3:21. The phrase “to be revealed” comes from the Greek word used in Romans 1:17, where it relates to the revelation of God’s righteousness in the gospel, and in Romans 1:18, where it concerns God’s wrath. This same word appears in Romans 1:19. For further insights, see Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2023.

⁷ In Romans 8:18 (12), the Greek (Grk) is translated (tn) as “are not worthy [to be compared].” Daniel B. Wallace, Senior New Testament Editor, *The NET Bible: New English Translation*, 2nd ed. (Richardson, TX: Biblical Studies Press, 1997), 2081.

mourning and crying and pain will be no more, for the first things have passed away.”⁸

Revelation 21:4 NET: “He will wipe away every tear from their eyes, and death will not exist anymore—or mourning, or crying, or pain, for the former things have ceased to exist.”⁹

III. Connection Between 2 Corinthians, Romans 8:18, and Revelation 21:4:

Romans 8:18 and 2 Corinthians 3:18 are deeply interconnected, both illuminating the transformation awaiting believers and the glorious future that will be fully revealed. These passages focus on the themes of glory and transformation, offering profound hope for believers. Romans 8:18 assures that the present sufferings believers endure are nothing in comparison to the future glory that will be revealed in them. This future glory provides a hope that transcends the hardships of the present world, reminding believers of the eternal reward that awaits them. In contrast, 2 Corinthians 3:18 emphasizes the ongoing, progressive transformation of believers, who are being changed into the image of Christ “from glory to glory.” This passage speaks to the present work of the Holy Spirit in believers’ lives, gradually conforming them to Christ’s likeness. These two verses together indicate that the transformation believers undergo is both spiritual and physical, culminating in their ultimate glorification. Revelation 21:4 further affirms

⁸ In Revelation 21:4, God promises the renewal of creation, where sorrow, death, and pain are no more. Parallel verses include Revelation 7:16, Isaiah 25:8, and Isaiah 35:10. For further insights, see Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2228.

⁹ In Revelation 21:4, (21) the Greek phrase “καὶ ὁ Θεὸς ἐκεῖνον” (kai ho Theos ekeino) is translated as “God, and He.” Due to the length and complexity of the Greek sentence, a new sentence begins in the English translation at this point. The Greek word “καὶ” (kai) is not translated here, as it serves as a conjunction linking the clauses. Strong’s Numbers: #2532 (“and” or “also”), #3588 (“the”), #2316 (“God”), and #1565 (“that one” or “that person”). (22) The Greek verb “ἀπερχομαι” (aperchomai), translated as “to go out of existence,” conveys the meaning “to cease to exist, to pass away, to cease” in this context. Strong’s #565. See William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1090-1220; Daniel B. Wallace, Senior New Testament Editor, *The NET Bible: New English Translation*, 2nd ed. (Richardson, TX: Biblical Studies Press, 1997), 2300.

this transformation, pointing to the new creation where God will wipe away every tear, and death, mourning, crying, and pain will be no more. The future glory of this new creation is the ultimate fulfillment of God's redemptive plan, where all suffering is vanquished, and believers experience the full peace and presence of God. Together, these passages encourage perseverance through present struggles, assuring believers that their transformation and glorification are part of a greater, eternal hope in God's presence.

A. Present and Future Glory:

In 2 Corinthians 3:18, believers experience a present transformation as they behold God's glory and are progressively changed into His image through the Holy Spirit. This transformation is ongoing, as believers grow in holiness and reflect God's divine nature more clearly. Romans 8:18, however, shifts the focus to a future glory that will be fully revealed when believers are completely redeemed and glorified. While the present suffering feels intense, the future glory will far outweigh it, creating a stark contrast between temporary pain and eternal reward. Both passages link present and future glory, assuring believers that what they experience now is but a glimpse of the magnificent transformation to come.

B. Transformation into Glory:

Both passages convey that believers are being transformed into something more glorious. 2 Corinthians 3:18 presents this transformation as a continual process, moving "from glory to glory," where the believer's reflection of Christ deepens as they grow in faith. Romans 8:18, however, points to a final, ultimate revelation of glory that awaits believers when they are fully

conformed to the image of Christ. This ultimate glory includes both the spiritual and physical dimensions of transformation, where believers will experience complete redemption and glorification. Both verses, therefore, emphasize that this transformation is not static but is an ongoing, future reality that will be fully realized in God's presence.

C. Role of the Holy Spirit:

The Holy Spirit plays a central role in both passages. In 2 Corinthians 3:18, the Holy Spirit is the one who empowers believers' ongoing transformation, enabling them to be progressively conformed to Christ's image. It is through the Spirit that believers move "from glory to glory" in their spiritual growth. Similarly, in Romans 8:18, while the Holy Spirit is not explicitly mentioned, His work is implied, as He is the one who guarantees the future glory and hope of believers. The Holy Spirit, therefore, serves as the agent of both the present transformation and the future glorification, ensuring that believers will ultimately experience the complete fulfillment of God's promises.

D. The Renewal of Creation:

Revelation 21:4 provides the ultimate vision of the renewal of creation, where God will wipe away every tear and abolish death, mourning, crying, and pain. This verse encapsulates the culmination of God's redemptive work, where the brokenness and suffering of the present world are forever eradicated. In the new creation, the sorrows of earthly existence will be no more, and believers will fully experience the peace, joy, and presence of God. This promise offers profound hope, reminding believers that the suffering they endure now is temporary in light of the eternal glory that awaits them.

2 Corinthians 3:18 echoes this idea of transformation, describing believers as being conformed to Christ's image "from glory to glory," pointing to a gradual spiritual change that ultimately leads to the perfected state described in Revelation 21:4. Just as believers are being spiritually transformed into the likeness of Christ, Revelation 21:4 assures that their final transformation will be fully realized when suffering and death are wiped away in the new creation. Both passages highlight the believer's journey as one of progressive sanctification, which will culminate in the perfect, restored creation where all suffering is eradicated, and the glory of God is fully manifested. Revelation 21:4 assures believers that God's victory over sin and death will result in the restoration of a perfect creation, a reality anticipated by 2 Corinthians 3:18, where the final transformation into Christ's likeness will be completed, and believers will experience the fulfillment of all God's promises in His eternal presence.

IV. Historical and Cultural Context:

A. Corinth:

Corinth [KAWR-inth] was one of ancient Greece's most significant trade cities (Acts 18:1, Acts 19:1, and 2 Cor. 1:1). Located on the Isthmus of Corinth, between the Ionian Sea and the Aegean Sea, the city served as a vital link between Rome, the capital of the Roman Empire, and the East. The Apostle Paul established a thriving church in Corinth, consisting of a diverse group of people who were drawn to the city's opportunities for gambling, legalized temple prostitution, business ventures, and various forms of entertainment in the bustling first-century naval hub (1 Cor. 6:9-11). Although Paul founded the church around 51 AD (Acts 18:1-18), Corinth's history stretches back to around 10,000 BC, when ancient tribes first settled there. Always a center for

commerce, the city was already prosperous and known for its bronze, pottery, and shipbuilding nearly 800 years before Christ. The Greek poet Homer even referred to it as “wealthy Corinth” in 850 BC.¹⁰

B. Patmos:

Patmos [PAT-muhs] is a small, rocky island where the apostle John was exiled and where he wrote the Book of Revelation (Rev. 1:9-11). The island is approximately 16 kilometers (10 miles) long and 10 kilometers (6 miles) wide, located off the southwest coast of Asia Minor (modern-day Turkey). Due to its desolate and barren landscape, Patmos was used by the Romans as a place of exile for criminals, who were forced to work in the island's mines and quarries. Since Christians were considered criminals by the Roman emperor Domitian (c. 51–96 AD, ruled from 81–96 AD), the apostle John likely endured harsh conditions during his exile. Early Christian tradition suggests that John remained in exile for 18 months.¹¹

V. Matthew Henry’s Commentary on 2 Corinthians 3:18:

A. Matthew Henry 2 Corinthians 3:12-18:

Matthew Henry writes: (vv. 12-18) The duty of gospel ministers is to speak with great

¹⁰ Photograph of Corinth by Gustav Jeeninga. The image shows the ruins of Corinth, once one of the wealthiest and most immoral cities of the ancient world (1 Cor. 5:1; 6:9-11). Near the synagogue excavation site stands the magnificent judgment seat, adorned with blue and white marble, where Gallio, the Roman proconsul of Achaia, dismissed Paul’s case (Acts 18:12-17). Today, the partially ruined Temple of Apollo looms over the ancient marketplace. Herbert Lockyer, Sr., ed., *Nelson's Illustrated Bible Dictionary* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1986), 251-252.

¹¹ Photograph of Patmos by Religious News Service. The image shows the rocky, barren island of Patmos in the Mediterranean Sea (modern Turkey), where John was exiled and received the messages from God recorded in the Book of Revelation (Rev. 1:9-11). Herbert Lockyer, Sr., ed., *Nelson's Illustrated Bible Dictionary* (Nashville, TN: Thomas Nelson Publishers, 1986), 804-805.

clarity. The gospel dispensation is more transparent than the law. While the Israelites could not fully comprehend what was commanded, we, under the gospel, can. The privilege of those who receive the gospel surpasses that of those who lived under the law. Under the old covenant, people's minds were blinded (v. 14), and a veil covered their hearts (v. 15). However, there will come a time when this veil will be removed, and the people will turn to the Lord (v. 16). The condition of those who believe the gospel is much more blessed: they have freedom (v. 17) and enlightenment, for with unveiled faces, they behold the glory of the Lord (v. 18). While Moses uniquely had the privilege of conversing with God face to face, all true Christians now experience this direct communion with God. This light and liberty are transformative (v. 18), progressively shaping us until grace is fully realized in eternal glory.¹²

B. Critique and Analysis of Matthew Henry:

Matthew Henry's interpretation of 2 Corinthians 3:12-18 is insightful and emphasizes the contrast between the old and new covenants. His understanding that the gospel dispensation is more transparent than the law highlights the clarity with which Christians can grasp divine truth. However, while his emphasis on the "unveiled faces" of believers is valuable, he could more explicitly connect the transformative process described in verse 18 with the ongoing sanctification of believers. Furthermore, while Henry rightly identifies the veil as a symbol of spiritual blindness, a deeper exploration of the historical and cultural context of the Corinthians might provide a more detailed understanding of how Paul's words would have resonated with his audience. Lastly, Henry's point that all Christians now experience direct communion with God,

¹² *The Bethany Parallel Commentary on the New Testament: Three Classic Commentaries in One Volume* (Minneapolis, MN: Bethany House Publishers, 1983), 1062–1063.

like Moses, is profound, yet it would benefit from a stronger theological discussion of how this intimacy is experienced through the indwelling of the Holy Spirit, a theme Paul emphasizes elsewhere.

VI. Adam Clarke Commentary on 2 Corinthians 3:18:

A. Adam Clarke 2 Corinthians 3:18:

We all, with unveiled faces, behold the glory of the Lord. Unlike the Israelites, who were unable to look upon Moses, the mediator of the old covenant, and required him to veil his face, we as Christians can gaze upon God's glory openly. Just as we can clearly see our own reflection in a mirror, we behold the glorious promises and blessings of the gospel of Christ. As we contemplate these promises, we anticipate them with desire and hope, and we grasp them by faith. This faith transforms us from the glory represented in the gospel to the actual enjoyment of that glory—into the glorious image of righteousness and holiness that belongs to God.

This transformation happens through the Spirit of the Lord, the power of Christ's Spirit that brings the gospel's promises to life. As a result, we partake in the divine nature and escape the corruption of the world. This, I believe, is the general meaning of this verse. To explain further, the word "κατοπτρίζομαι" (katoptrizomenoi), translated as "beholding" in the phrase "in a glass," comes from the Greek words "κατά" (kata, meaning "against" or "according to") and "ὀπτόμαι" (optomai, meaning "to look" or "to see"), which refers to looking into a mirror or

discerning something through reflected light.¹³ Mirrors in the ancient world, used by the Jews, Greeks, and Romans, were often made of highly polished metal (see 1 Cor. 13:12), and in strong light, they would reflect the face in a brightly illuminated manner. This is the image Paul is likely referring to.

Just as the light in a polished mirror illuminates the face, so does the gospel of Jesus, when earnestly contemplated and believed, illuminate the soul with divine splendor. The gospel reflects the image of Christ to the believer, displaying His perfections. As we believe and receive the influence of the Holy Spirit, our lives are progressively transformed into that same image—the image of God, which was lost in the fall but is now restored through Jesus Christ.¹⁴

B. Critique and Analysis of Adam Clarke:

Adam Clarke’s commentary on 2 Corinthians 3:18 provide a clear and insightful interpretation of the passage, highlighting the transformative power of the gospel. His explanation contrasts the veil placed over Moses’ face with the unveiled access Christians now have to God’s glory, emphasizing the openness and clarity of the new covenant. Clarke effectively uses the metaphor of the mirror, illustrating how the gospel, when reflected upon and believed, illuminates the soul, guiding the believer toward transformation into the image of Christ.

¹³ The Greek word “κατοπτρίζομαι” (katoptrizomenoi), (Strong’s #2734), translated as “beholding” in the phrase “in a glass,” is derived from the Greek words “κατά” (kata, meaning “against” or “according to”) (Strong’s #2596) and “ὀπτόμαι” (optomai, meaning “to look” or “to see”) (Strong’s #3700). It refers to looking into a mirror or discerning something through reflected light. See William D. Mounce, *Mounce’s Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1180-1225.

¹⁴ *The Bethany Parallel Commentary on the New Testament: Three Classic Commentaries in One Volume* (Minneapolis, MN: Bethany House Publishers, 1983), 1062–1063.

However, there are areas where Clarke's commentary could be further refined. First, while the comparison between Moses and the Christian believer is appropriate, Clarke's interpretation may be overly idealized in terms of the believer's immediate transformation. The process of transformation is often more gradual and requires continued sanctification, not just an initial act of beholding. Clarke also refers to "the divine nature" and "escaping the corruption of the world," which could benefit from additional clarification, as these theological ideas carry deep implications for Christian living. The language of "partaking in the divine nature" is taken from 2 Peter 1:4 and could be more carefully linked to Pauline theology to avoid potential confusion.

Additionally, while Clarke's historical explanation of the use of *mirrors* in the ancient world adds depth, it would be helpful to draw more direct connections between the imagery of the *mirror* and its implications for how the believer engages with Scripture or experiences spiritual formation. The commentary could also explore more explicitly how the transformative process relates to the ongoing work of the Holy Spirit, especially in light of the context of 2 Corinthians 3, which deals with the ministry of the Spirit versus the law.

VII. Michael Gorman's Commentary on 2 Corinthians 3:18:

A. The Ministry of the New Covenant:

This passage explores Paul's reflections on the old and new covenants, particularly in 2 Corinthians 3:1-18. It highlights the transition from the "old covenant" represented by the Ten Commandments written on stone tablets, to the "new covenant" written on human hearts through the Spirit. Paul is not denigrating the Law and the covenant it represents; rather, he is praising

the new covenant because of its surpassing greatness and glory vis-à-vis the already glorious first covenant, comparing the greater with the lesser (not the worthless).¹⁵ Paul draws a contrast between the two but is not criticizing the old covenant. Instead, he acknowledges its glory while affirming that the new covenant is even more glorious. Paul's point is that while the old covenant came with glory (as seen in Moses' shining face when he received the tablets after the incident with the golden calf in Exodus 32 and 34), the new covenant surpasses it because it brings even greater glory through Christ. Despite focusing on the end of the old covenant, Paul emphasizes that there's still a link between God's promises then and now, as all of God's promises are fulfilled in Christ (2 Corinthians 1:20). Now, the glory of God is accessible to everyone who turns to the Lord (2 Corinthians 3:18).

However, Paul's explanation about who this "Lord" is can seem confusing. He first suggests that the Lord is Jesus, but then he also equates the Lord with the Spirit (2 Corinthians 3:17). This does not mean the Lord is neither God the Father (YHWH) nor Jesus. Instead, Paul appears to indicate that the Spirit is connected with both YHWH and Jesus. The glory of Israel's God is perceived only by "beholding," through the Spirit's work¹⁶, the glory of his "image," the (crucified and resurrected) Lord Jesus (4:4), like an image reflected in a mirror (3:18). For Paul, the glory of God can only be truly seen by looking at Jesus, who is the image of God. Through the Spirit, believers can behold this glory, which transforms them to be more like Christ (Romans 8:29). This transformation involves a journey "from glory to glory," which Paul likely

¹⁵ Michael J. Gorman contrasts the old covenant with the new covenant: the old covenant is characterized by "the letter (3:6), a ministry of death (3:6, 7), written on stone tablets (3:3, 7), came with glory (3:7), a ministry of condemnation (3:9), now set aside along with its glory (3:7, 10-11)," while the new covenant is described as "of the Spirit (3:6), giving life (3:6), written on human hearts (3:3), coming in greater glory (3:10-11), a ministry of justification and righteousness (3:9), and being permanent (3:11)." Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2017), 355.

¹⁶ The phrase "we are being transformed" is a 'divine passive,' indicating the Spirit's work (cf. Rom. 12:1-2; Mark 9:2; Matt. 17:2 [the Transfiguration]). The visual metaphor in this passage is challenging to translate and has been interpreted as both seeing and reflecting. Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2017), 356.

means as moving from the current, cross-shaped glory (the suffering and humility of Christ) to the full glory of resurrection in the future (Romans 5:2; 1 Corinthians 15:42-54; Philippians 3:21).¹⁷

B. Critique and Analysis of Michael Gorman:

Michael Gorman's commentary on 2 Corinthians 3:1-18 provides a thoughtful and detailed exploration of Paul's reflections on the old and new covenants. Gorman succeeds in emphasizing that Paul does not dismiss the value of the old covenant; rather, he recognizes its glory while highlighting the greater glory of the new covenant through Christ. This balance between continuity and discontinuity is well captured, as Gorman affirms that Paul sees the promises of God fulfilled in Christ, thus connecting the old with the new. However, Gorman's analysis becomes complex when addressing Paul's fluid use of the term "Lord," suggesting it can refer to Jesus, the Spirit, or even YHWH. While he rightly highlights the interconnectedness of Jesus and the Spirit, his explanation may leave readers struggling to grasp Paul's precise theological distinctions. The commentary could benefit from clearer delineation, as the discussion risks bordering on ambiguity rather than expounding Paul's intended meaning. Additionally, while Gorman's focus on transformation "from glory to glory" is insightful, his interpretation of this phrase as moving from cross-shaped glory to resurrection glory could have been better contextualized within Paul's broader theology of suffering and glory. Nonetheless, Gorman's analysis is a commendable contribution that deepens the reader's understanding of this

¹⁷ The Greek phrase "ἀπὸ δόξης εἰς δόξαν" (apo doxēs eis doxan), meaning "from glory to glory," appears in 2 Corinthians 3:18. The Strong's Concordance numbers for this phrase are: "ἀπὸ" (apo) – Strong's #575, "δόξης" (doxēs) – Strong's #1391, "εἰς" (eis) – Strong's #1519, and "δόξαν" (doxan) – Strong's #1391. See William D. Mounce, *Mounce's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1127-1133; Michael J. Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2017), 354-356.

challenging passage.

VIII. The Pillar New Testament Commentary (PNTC): 2 Corinthians by Mark Seifrid:

A. Pages 204-206, 2 Corinthians 3:18 – The Pillar New Testament Commentary:

In his final formulation of the letter-Spirit contrast, Paul revisits the conclusion of verse 7: the glory of Moses' face and the ministry of death have been abolished. This glory has been superseded. Paul anticipates the argument he will make in verses 12-18, while returning to his original claim that divine glory attends the ministry of the Spirit: "For if that which is done away with [came about] through glory, how much more [does] that which abides [do so] in glory." Paul now develops the letter-Spirit paradox further, showing that the contrast between the temporary nature of the old covenant (rescinded) and the eternal nature of the new covenant (abiding) supports his opening assertion: "The letter kills, but the Spirit gives life." The first is temporary, while the second is eternal. Paul's description of divine glory in relation to the two covenants evolves slightly. The glory of the old covenant, which has been abolished, came "through glory," but the glory of the new covenant remains "in glory." While Moses' ministry had a divine glory, this glory was not inherent in it but was only mediated through it—it was an "alien" glory. In contrast, the ministry of the Spirit and righteousness is enveloped in divine glory that rightfully belongs to it.¹⁸

The concept of boldness and free speech "*παρρησία*" (*parrēsia*), is typically translated as "boldness," "confidence," or "openness" (as in 2 Cor. 3:12). This reflects the freedom that

¹⁸ Mark A. Seifrid, *The Second Letter to the Corinthians*, Pillar New Testament Commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2014), 204-206.

accompanies the presence of the Spirit (v. 18).¹⁹ For further reflections on this theme, see W.C. Van Unnik, *The Christian's Freedom of Speech in the New Testament*, BJRL 44 (1962): 466-488.²⁰ I thank Dr. Jeffrey Oschwald (c. 1955-) for providing this reference. Paul's confidence stems from his complete assurance that the Corinthians themselves are "a letter of Christ," in whom Christ is present despite outward appearances. Through the new covenant, the Spirit is with them, granting them a vision of God's glory. Consequently, Paul, as an apostle of Christ, needs no external confirmation or commendation. His boldness is unparalleled, arising from the hope found in the new covenant, which compels him to speak. This openness of Paul's speech also reflects his open heart toward the Corinthians, as he will later express (2 Cor. 6:11). Paul's boldness is deeply tied to the weakness and suffering he endures as an apostle—suffering that is repulsive to the Corinthians. He has already discussed this suffering (2 Cor. 1:3-11) and will address it again (2 Cor. 4:7-15). As noted, Paul suffers primarily for his churches, especially for the wayward Corinthians.²¹

B. Pages 218-222, 2 Corinthians 3:18 – The Pillar New Testament Commentary:

In his final elaboration of the Exodus narrative, Paul revisits the claims made in verses 7-11, emphasizing that the mission of the new covenant is accompanied by glory despite outward appearances. This completes his argument that the Corinthians themselves serve as his apostolic

¹⁹ The Greek word "παρρησία" (*parrēsia*) is typically translated as "boldness," "confidence," or "openness". Strong's number #3954. It is used 31 times in the New Testament (NT). Used in Acts 2:29, 4:13, 2 Cor. 7:4, and Eph. 3:12. See William D. Mounce, *Mounce's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1237.

²⁰ See W.C. van Unnik, "The Christian's Freedom of Speech in the New Testament," *British Journal of Religious Literature* 44 (1962): 466-488.

²¹ Mark A. Seifrid, *The Second Letter to the Corinthians*, Pillar New Testament Commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2014), 206.

letter of commendation. It is not only the apostle who contrasts with Moses, but also the Corinthians, who are now part of his mission: “we all...are transformed from glory to glory.” Unlike the glory of the old covenant, which was given only to Moses, the glory of the new covenant is communicated to all in Christ. However, the shared vision of the Lord’s glory does not diminish Paul’s authority as an emissary of the new covenant. This authority is central to his argument in this letter (see the discussion of Paul as co-worker in 1:24, pp. 71-72 above). Christian ministry—and indeed all human relationships—must embody the balance of authority and submission with equality, as reflected not only in the relationship between pastors and churches but also in family dynamics, such as between parents and children or husbands and wives.²²

As noted, Moses’ encounter with the Lord in Exodus is fundamentally a verbal exchange, even though it includes a visual element. From this verbal communication, Moses’ face shone (Exod. 34:29, 35). This verbal encounter is reminiscent of earlier descriptions in Exodus 33:11, where the Lord speaks to Moses “face-to-face as one speaks to a friend.” The verbal aspect remains central, though it is associated with the visual encounter. A similar tradition appears in Numbers 12:6-8, where Moses is distinguished from the prophets by speaking with the Lord “mouth to mouth, as a vision not in riddles,” and “he beholds the form of the Lord.” This passage underscores that the Lord’s communication with Moses was primarily verbal but had a visual dimension. Deuteronomy 34:10 echoes this idea, affirming that Moses is unique because of his face-to-face relationship with the Lord.²³

²² See O. Bayer, *Freiheit als Antwort: Zur theologischen Ethik* [Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 1995], 55-59.

²³ Mark A. Seifrid, *The Second Letter to the Corinthians*, Pillar New Testament Commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2014), 218-220.

In contrast, Paul emphasizes that believers' encounter with the Lord is visual, setting it apart from the "letter" of the old covenant. In verses 12-18, Paul articulates the noetic effects of judgment and salvation, expressed through visual metaphors. However, Paul does not negate the Exodus tradition; rather, he applies it to his apostolic ministry. His claim to an unhindered vision of divine glory defends the mission of the new covenant, i.e., the apostolic proclamation of the Gospel. He refuses to "corrupt" the Word of God (4:2). In 4:1-6, Paul describes the proclamation of the Gospel as a gift of light, to which only unbelievers remain blind. In verse 14, Paul interprets "seeing" as "hearing." The veil that blocks the vision of divine glory lies over the reading of the old covenant. The visual language in verse 18 mirrors this synesthetic metaphor, recalling the similar metaphor of 2:14-15. Both metaphors illustrate the failure of human understanding, which often relies on what is outwardly visible, to properly know God. In Christ, God's comfort, life, and righteousness are concealed behind suffering and the cross. This divine work can only be perceived through faith, which comes through hearing the apostolic word. Paul is not bypassing his apostolic proclamation with visual imagery; rather, he is describing it. His equality with the Corinthians in perceiving the Lord's glory does not undermine his apostolic authority but reinforces it.²⁴

C. Pages 241-242, 2 Corinthians 3:18 – *The Pillar New Testament Commentary*:

In *The Pillar New Testament Commentary* on *2 Corinthians*, it is emphasized that the word of the Creator has brought light into Paul's heart, just as the Gospel illuminates the hearts of unbelievers, who remain blind to it. While Paul distinguishes his apostolic encounter with God from the experiences of other Christians, the fundamental nature of his encounter is still verbal,

²⁴ Mark A. Seifrid, *The Second Letter to the Corinthians*, Pillar New Testament Commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2014), 221-222.

similar to theirs. Furthermore, by using the plural form when describing his “enlightenment,” Paul broadens the significance of his experience, extending it to others who, unlike him, did not witness the risen Christ on the Damascus road. Paul clearly refers to his own conversion experience, implicitly recalling his vision of the risen Christ (cf. 1 Cor. 9:1). However, he only alludes to this outward vision in passing, as he no longer knows Christ “according to the flesh” (2 Cor. 5:16). Even as he recalls his vision, it remains a prolepsis, a foretaste, of the final day of the Lord.

One could interpret Paul’s language as referring to “the glory of God in the person of Jesus Christ.” While this interpretation might obscure the connection with 2 Corinthians 3:18, it would more clearly convey Paul’s thought: God’s glory, though hidden in the crucified and risen Jesus, is nevertheless displayed. This vision of God’s glory, though real, remains indirect and eschatological in nature. We do not yet see it “face-to-face” (1 Cor. 13:12), and the light of the Gospel and God’s glory in Christ reaches us through hearing.²⁵

D. Critique and Review of *The Pillar New Testament Commentary (PNTC): 2 Corinthians*

Mark Seifrid’s contribution to *The Pillar New Testament Commentary* (PNTC) series offers a thorough, well-researched, and theologically rich exegesis of *2 Corinthians*. Seifrid, a seasoned scholar in New Testament studies, brings a scholarly yet pastoral approach to this epistle, blending academic rigor with practical insights. His work is valuable both for scholars and for those in ministry seeking to understand the text deeply.

Strengths:

²⁵ Mark A. Seifrid, *The Second Letter to the Corinthians*, Pillar New Testament Commentary (Grand Rapids, MI: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2014), 241-242.

(1) Historical and Theological Context: Seifrid excels in situating *2 Corinthians* within its historical and theological context. His exploration of Paul's apostolic authority and the role of suffering within the Christian life is insightful. Seifrid does not merely focus on the individual verses but carefully considers the broader narrative and theological implications of the letter. The way he integrates Paul's personal suffering with his theological reflections offers a compelling vision of the Apostle's ministry, emphasizing how the cross-shaped life relates to the new covenant.

(2) Clear Exegesis: Seifrid's exegesis is grounded in a solid understanding of Greek, and his treatment of the text is meticulous. He handles difficult passages with clarity, offering multiple interpretive options and providing a reasoned defense for his conclusions. His discussion of the letter-spirit contrast (2 Cor. 3) and the nature of divine glory in the new covenant is one of the highlights of the commentary. For example, his distinction between the "alien" glory of Moses' ministry and the "inherent" glory of the Spirit-filled life is both subtle and profound, shedding light on Paul's theology of glory.

(3) Theological Depth: A key strength of Seifrid's commentary is his theological depth. He consistently ties the text back to larger doctrinal themes, such as the nature of the new covenant, the ministry of the Spirit, and the transformative power of the gospel. Seifrid's discussions are particularly engaging when exploring the implications of Paul's apostolic mission, his view of human weakness, and the sufficiency of God's grace in the midst of affliction. These reflections are timely and pertinent, given the contemporary church's ongoing struggles with suffering and the misunderstanding of Christian ministry.

(4) Accessibility: While deeply scholarly, Seifrid's commentary remains accessible to a wide audience. He writes in a style that is engaging and clear, without overly technical jargon, making it a helpful resource for pastors, seminarians, and interested lay readers. The commentary is designed to be practical, offering insights that can be applied in preaching and teaching. It includes valuable sections on application, making it relevant for ministry and pastoral care.

Weaknesses:

(1) Limited Interaction with Contemporary Scholarship: One area where Seifrid's commentary could improve is in its engagement with more recent scholarly debates. While he interacts with a broad range of sources, there is room for greater engagement with modern critical perspectives, especially those that delve into the socio-rhetorical or literary dimensions of the text. Contemporary commentaries often benefit from a wider interaction with feminist, postcolonial, or social-scientific approaches, which Seifrid touches on but does not fully explore.

(2) Occasional Lack of Depth on Specific Cultural Practices: Seifrid's focus is primarily on the theological and literary aspects of the text, and while this is valuable, there are moments where the cultural or social background of 2 Corinthians could have been explored more deeply. For instance, Paul's interaction with the Corinthians and his rhetorical strategy could have been unpacked with more attention to the Greco-Roman context, which would further enrich our understanding of the letter's nuances.

(3) Theological Bias: Seifrid's theological perspective is generally conservative and Reformed, which is clearly evident throughout the commentary. While this does not undermine the commentary's value, readers from different theological traditions (such as Arminian or

Pentecostal) might find his interpretations less resonant with their perspectives, particularly when discussing topics like election, grace, and the nature of salvation. Seifrid's Reformed lens shapes his interpretation of key passages, such as the implications of the new covenant and the nature of Paul's apostolic authority.

Conclusion:

Overall, Mark Seifrid's *The Pillar New Testament Commentary: 2 Corinthians* stands as a substantial contribution to biblical scholarship. His clear exegesis, theological depth, and practical application make this commentary invaluable to pastors, seminarians, and anyone seeking to understand Paul's letter to the Corinthians. Despite some minor limitations in cultural and contemporary scholarly engagement, Seifrid's work remains an essential resource for those seeking to delve deeply into the theology of *2 Corinthians* and its implications for the Christian life.

IX. Word Biblical Commentary (WBC) on 2 Corinthians by Ralph Martin:

A. 2 Corinthians 3:18 – A Mirror “To Behold”:

In 2 Corinthians 3:18, Paul concludes his profound discussion on the transformative work of the Spirit, emphasizing the shift from the old covenant to the new. The phrase “but we all” serves to broaden the impact of the Holy Spirit’s work, not just limited to Paul or the apostles, but to all believers. For Paul, Christ is the ultimate revelation of God’s image—He embodies the new covenant that Paul, as a servant, proclaims. This new covenant is marked by a new creation (cf. 2 Corinthians 5:17) where the old era of the law gives way to the new age of salvation and righteousness inaugurated by Christ. Unlike the old covenant, which was veiled and hidden, the new covenant allows believers to see God’s glory unveiled in Christ.

Paul uses the metaphor of a mirror to describe how Christians “behold” or “reflect” the Lord’s glory. The Greek word “κατοπτρίζομαι” (katoptrizomenoi) can mean both to behold and to reflect, but here, the translation “beholding” seems preferable.²⁶ This interpretation contrasts believers who can see God’s glory clearly, with the Jews who, metaphorically speaking, are still veiled and unable to perceive it due to unbelief. This view is supported by scholars like Werner G. Kümmel (c. 1905 – 1995 AD), who argue that the term “beholding” better maintains the contrast between the unveiled clarity of the new covenant and the veiled obscurity of the old. The participle used here refers to beholding God’s glory as it is revealed in the “image” of Christ (cf. 2 Corinthians 4:4-6; Colossians 1:15; Hebrews 1:1-4). Christ, as the perfect image of God,

²⁶ In 2 Corinthians 3:18, the Greek word “κατοπτρίζομενοι” (katoptrizomenoi) which translates to “beholding or “reflecting” the glory of the Lord, depending on the interpretation of the passage. Strong’s #2734. The word metaphorically refers to gazing into “a mirror” and seeing “a reflection,” which symbolizes perceiving and being transformed by God’s glory. See William D. Mounce, Mounce’s *Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1187.

serves as the prototype for all believers, who are being transformed into His likeness. This transformation process is dynamic and ongoing, linking to Paul's broader theological framework in passages like 1 Corinthians 15:44-49, where believers are destined to bear the image of the heavenly Christ.²⁷

Paul's discussion of the covenants in verses 7-18 presents a series of contrasts: the old covenant, represented by the Mosaic law, is characterized by glory that fades, whereas the new covenant, in Christ, offers a glory that is permanent and surpassing. The old covenant set a standard for holiness but lacked the power to enable people to meet it, effectively becoming a "ministry of death" (2 Corinthians 3:7) and "condemnation" (3:9). Paul acknowledges that while the law was good (cf. Romans 7:12-14), it ultimately led to death because it demanded perfection from inherently weak human beings. Paul further argues that the law, while glorious, was always meant to be temporary. Its fading glory, symbolized by the diminishing radiance of Moses' face (cf. Exodus 34:29-35), highlights its impermanence. The fading splendor of Moses' face signifies the transitory nature of the old covenant, which has now been surpassed by the enduring glory of the Gospel. This Gospel not only fulfills the law but reveals God's glory in Christ, inviting believers to experience transformation and freedom through the Spirit. Thus, what was once hidden and veiled in the law has been fully unveiled and illuminated in Christ, offering believers a direct and transformative encounter with God's glory.²⁸

B. 2 Corinthians 3:18 (New Covenant) vs. (Old Covenant) Exodus 34:29-35 (NRSV):

²⁷ Ralph P. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, vol. 40 of *Word Biblical Commentary*, ed. David A. Hubbard and Glenn W. Barker (Waco, TX: Word Books Publisher, 1986), 72–74.

²⁸ Ralph P. Martin, *2 Corinthians*, vol. 40 of *Word Biblical Commentary*, ed. David A. Hubbard and Glenn W. Barker (Waco, TX: Word Books Publisher, 1986), 73–75.

*Moses came down from Mount Sinai. As he came down from the mountain with the two tablets of the covenant in his hand, Moses did not know that the skin of his face shone because he had been talking with God. When Aaron and all the Israelites saw Moses, the skin of his face was shining, and they were afraid to come near him. But Moses called to them; and Aaron and all the leaders of the congregation returned to him, and Moses spoke with them. Afterward all the Israelites came near, and he gave them in commandment all that the Lord had spoken with him on Mount Sinai. When Moses had finished speaking with them, he put a veil on his face; but whenever Moses went in before the Lord to speak with him, he would take the veil off, until he came out; and when he came out, and told the Israelites what he had been commanded, the Israelites would see the face of Moses, that the skin of his face was shining; and Moses would put the veil on his face again, until he went in to speak with him.*²⁹

C. Exegesis of 2 Corinthians 3:18:

The Apostle Paul's second letter to the Corinthians is a profound discourse on the nature of the New Covenant, the ministry of the Spirit, and the transformative power of Christ. One of the most theologically rich verses in this letter is 2 Corinthians 3:18 NRSV:

²⁹ Exodus 34:29-35 (v. 35): The Hebrew terms "shone" and "shining" are more accurately translated as "radiant." For additional insights, see Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 134.

“And all of us, with unveiled faces, seeing the glory of the Lord as though reflected in a mirror, are being transformed into the same image from one degree of glory to another; for this comes from the Lord, the Spirit”³⁰

This verse encapsulates Paul’s message of spiritual transformation through the work of the Holy Spirit, where believers are continually shaped into the likeness of Christ. In examining this text, we will explore the immediate context, the meaning of its key terms, and its implications for the believer's life.

D. Contextual Background:

To fully appreciate 2 Corinthians 3:18, it is essential to understand the broader context of chapter 3, where Paul contrasts the Old and New Covenants. He uses the story of Moses in Exodus 34:29-35, where Moses' face shone after encountering God on Mount Sinai. However, Moses covered his face with a veil to shield the Israelites from the fading glory. Paul draws a parallel between this veil and the spiritual blindness that prevented the Israelites from fully grasping the glory of the Old Covenant. He asserts that in Christ, the veil is removed, allowing believers to see God’s glory directly (2 Cor. 3:14-16).

In verses leading up to 3:18, Paul speaks about the surpassing glory of the New Covenant, which is mediated through the Spirit and not through the written law. The New Covenant brings life, righteousness, and freedom in contrast to the Old Covenant, which was characterized by

³⁰ In 2 Corinthians 3:18: The phrase “All of us” continues Paul’s emphasis on universality throughout the Corinthian letters. The reference to “unveiled faces” echoes Moses’ repeated unveiling in Exodus 34:34. The mention of glory “reflected in a mirror” may suggest the reflection of God’s glory in Christ (2 Cor. 4:6). Some translations render the verb differently, such as “to behold” or “to contemplate.” The idea of transformation into the divine image has roots in Hellenistic religion, as well as in Romans 8:29, 1 Corinthians 15:49, and Colossians 3:10. See Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2065.

condemnation and death (2 Cor. 3:6-9). Thus, 2 Corinthians 3:18 serves as a climactic conclusion to this section, emphasizing the transformative nature of the Spirit's work in believers.

E. Critique and Review of *Word Biblical Commentary: 2 Corinthians*

Strengths:

(1) Thoughtful Exegesis: Ralph Martin's exegesis of 2 Corinthians 3:18, as presented in the *Word Biblical Commentary* (WBC), is thorough and insightful, particularly in its emphasis on the theological significance of the new covenant and the transformative power of the Spirit. A key strength is Martin's detailed analysis of the Greek term “κατοπτρίζομαι” (katoptrizomenoi), which he translates as “beholding” rather than “reflecting.” By opting for this translation, Martin aligns with scholars like Werner G. Kümmel in maintaining the contrast Paul draws between the unveiled clarity available to believers under the new covenant and the obscurity that characterized the old covenant. This detailed translation choice enriches our understanding of the believer's direct and transformative encounter with God's glory in Christ.

(2) Incorporation of Old Testament: Another strength of Martin's commentary is his exploration of the Old Testament background, particularly Exodus 34:29-35. By drawing parallels between Moses' veiled face and the spiritual blindness of the Israelites, Martin effectively illuminates Paul's argument about the surpassing and permanent glory of the new covenant. His theological reflection on the “ministry of death” (2 Cor. 3:7) versus the life-giving ministry of the Spirit is particularly compelling. Martin underscores that while the Mosaic law

was good, its temporary nature and inability to empower adherence highlight the superiority of the new covenant, which grants believers righteousness and freedom through the Spirit.

(3) Continual Transformation: Furthermore, Martin’s emphasis on the continual transformation of believers into the likeness of Christ (cf. 2 Cor. 3:18; 4:4-6) is a strength that resonates with Paul’s broader eschatological themes. This perspective highlights the dynamic nature of Christian sanctification, where believers are progressively conformed to Christ’s image—a theme Paul further develops in passages like 1 Corinthians 15:44-49.

Weaknesses:

(1) Reliance on one interpretation: While Martin’s exegesis offers many valuable insights, there are areas where it could be critiqued. One notable weakness is the reliance on the interpretation of “κατοπτρίζομαι” as solely “beholding.” Although this translation is well-supported, some scholars argue that it also carries the connotation of “reflecting” God’s glory, suggesting a dual meaning where believers both see and reflect Christ’s glory to the world. By favoring only one interpretation (he touches on other translations such as ‘reflecting,’ but primarily focuses on ‘beholding’), Martin potentially overlooks the rich interplay between seeing and reflecting, which can signify the believer’s role in embodying and radiating God’s transformative presence.

(2) Further explanation of “ministry of condemnation”: Additionally, while Martin addresses the contrast between the old and new covenants, his treatment of the “ministry of condemnation” could have delved deeper into the implications for contemporary readers. Although he touches on the temporary nature of the law, further exploration of how the new covenant enables

believers to fulfill the righteous requirements of the law would strengthen the commentary's practical application. This could help bridge the gap between the historical-theological context of Paul's letters and modern Christian living.

(3) Lack of Scholarly Opinions: Another area of critique is the occasional lack of engagement with diverse scholarly opinions. While Martin references Kümmel, expanding the range of scholarly dialogue could enrich the discussion. Engaging with other contemporary voices might provide a more balanced perspective on contentious issues like the meaning of the veil or the interpretation of Paul's metaphor of transformation.

Conclusion:

Overall, Ralph Martin's *WBC* commentary on 2 Corinthians 3:18 offers a comprehensive and theologically rich exploration of Paul's message regarding the new covenant. The strengths lie in Martin's robust analysis of Greek terms, his skillful integration of Old Testament narratives, and his emphasis on the ongoing transformation of believers into Christ's image. However, the commentary would benefit from a more nuanced exploration of key Greek terms and a deeper engagement with a broader range of scholarly interpretations. Despite these critiques, Martin's work remains a valuable resource for those seeking to understand Paul's teachings on the new covenant, the Spirit's transformative work, and the surpassing glory of Christ that believers are invited to behold and reflect.

X. Conclusion

In conclusion, a thorough exploration of 2 Corinthians 3:18, including its connections to Romans 8:18 and Revelation 21:4, offers profound insights into the transformation and future

hope of believers. Through examining the historical and cultural context, as well as insights from respected commentators such as Matthew Henry, Adam Clarke, Michael Gorman, Mark Seifrid in the *Pillar New Testament Commentary*, and Ralph Martin in the *Word Biblical Commentary*, we see a unified theme of spiritual transformation that culminates in the ultimate glorification of the believer. The verse, while grounded in the immediate context of Paul's letters, points to the eschatological hope shared across Scripture that believers are being progressively transformed into the likeness of Christ, with an eternal future that promises the full realization of God's glory. Each commentary, offering unique perspectives, enriches our understanding of this pivotal verse, helping us grasp the depth of the Christian's journey from present suffering to future glory. This theological progression challenges believers to reflect on their own transformation and encourages them with the promise of a future where all suffering will be wiped away in the presence of God's glory.

The various commentaries reviewed in this study emphasize different aspects of 2 Corinthians 3:18, yet all converge on the theme of transformative sanctification and the future fulfillment of God's promises. By looking into the theological insights of figures like Henry, Clarke, Gorman, Seifrid, and Martin, we gain a fuller understanding of how the apostolic message of transformation in Christ resonates both in the present and in the anticipated future. The interplay between suffering, glory, and transformation encourages believers to live with a renewed perspective, looking toward the eternal weight of glory that outweighs present trials. Ultimately, this examination highlights the centrality of the Gospel message in shaping not only the individual believer's life but also the collective hope of the Church.

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